

OpenCitations: an open infrastructure enabling Open Research Information

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OpenCitations is a scholarly infrastructure dedicated to making citation and bibliographic metadata openly available and freely reusable, supporting the principles of Open Science (Peroni and Shotton, 2020). Established in 2010, OpenCitations addresses the long-standing issue of citation data being locked behind proprietary systems by offering an open, interoperable, and sustainable alternative. Its mission is to harvest, preserve, and disseminate high-quality scholarly metadata in both human- and machine-readable formats, all released under the CC0 public domain waiver.

As a disruptive player in the scholarly communication ecosystem, OpenCitations enables transparent and reproducible research evaluation through its open citation indexes and services. These include the OpenCitations Index (Heibi et al., 2024) of Citations and OpenCitations Meta (Massari et al., 2024), both of which are accessible via data dumps, REST APIs, and SPARQL endpoints. The infrastructure is committed to the FAIR principles and adheres to initiatives such as I4OC and I4OA. Furthermore, OpenCitations is deeply committed to the principles outlined in the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (Kramer et al., 2024), of which it is an active supporter. The Declaration calls for a systemic shift in the way research information is produced, used, and governed, emphasizing that such information should be open by default, and that its supporting infrastructures must be sustainable, transparent, and community-led. The alignment with the Declaration not only reinforces OpenCitations' operational principles but also situates it as a key enabler of the broader shift toward an open and equitable research information ecosystem.

From a technical perspective, OpenCitations continuously integrates citation data from a range of trusted sources, including Crossref (Hendricks et al., 2020), DataCite (Group et al., 2024), NIH-OCC (Hutchins et al., 2019), OpenAIRE (Manghi et al., 2012), and JaLC (Kato et al., 2012). The metadata and citation links harvested from these sources are processed through a dedicated ingestion workflow and stored in OpenCitations' two main datasets: OpenCitations Index (citation links) and OpenCitations Meta (bibliographic metadata). As of now, over 2.1 billion unique citations have been stored, and this number continues to grow as new data is regularly integrated from both existing and upcoming sources.

Beyond infrastructure, OpenCitations collaborates with a wide network of Open Science infrastructures and organizations, and is actively involved in communities that aim to build a more equitable and open research environment. Its impact is tangible in its systemic use as a source of citation data by a wide range of tools and projects. Moreover, its visibility and reach are amplified by its inclusion in major Open Science catalogues.

OpenCitations works for the community and with the community. But in a time when scholarly infrastructures face growing pressure from commercialization, financial precarity, and

systemic opacity, building truly open, inclusive, and sustainable alternatives is no longer just an option: it's a necessity.

By making citation data a public good, and by upholding openness not just as a technical choice but as a commitment, OpenCitations positions itself as a catalyst for change in the scholarly ecosystem.

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